

easyFCDR Quick Start Guide

FCDR = Fundamental Climate Data Record

Main contents:

- brightness temperatures & reflectances, tabulated radiances
- uncertainty estimates and error correlation information
- geospatial information, spectral response functions

Principal variables to explore:

- $Ch\{X\}$ – the radiance/BT/reflectance for channel X with spectral response function
- $u_{\{type\}}Ch\{X\}$ – one of three components of uncertainty of different type (independent, structured, common)
- $channel_correlation_matrix_{\{type\}}$ & $cross_{\{pixel\}}_correlation_coefficients$ – quantifying the degree of correlation between errors (across channels or across pixels (cross-line or -element))
- pixels not to use and quality flags
- Latitude, longitude, time, sun and satellite angles

What is the uncertainty information useful for?

- enabling the uncertainty from radiance/BT/reflectance to inform the uncertainty attributable to variables that you retrieve
- use the uncertainty propagation tool to illustrate this for one-pixel-at-a-time retrieval functions

How do the uncertainty types (independent, structured and common) map onto “traditional” uncertainty names?

For more information see the Product User Guide.
Other current FCDRs available: MVIRI, HIRS, MW